

1 Gna14 expression during lineage specification in the embryo.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Gna14
9 as a marker of lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Lim, Y.H., Bacchiocchi, A., Qiu, J., Straub, R., Bruckner, A., Bercovitch, L., Narayan, D., McNiff, J.,
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